

Architecturally Driven BIM Processes with Practical Explorations

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Abstract

This thesis explores the role of BIM in architectural practice, highlighting its identity as a methodology centered on optimizing work processes rather than a creative design approach. Despite its transformative potential, BIM faces challenges like ¿ how to make BIM more appealing to architects and designers? it is essential to address them to enhance its design tools. BIM's future entails revolutionizing architectural design by streamlining workflows, fostering creativity, and contributing to the ongoing advancement of the AEC industry.

For the exploratory methods, I did participatory research Collaborating with Dekleva Gregorič Architects, a renowned Slovenian architectural firm in Ljubljana, exploring their transition to BIM with real-world case studies, illustrating their relevance to any architectural practice, starting with BIM implementation, incorporation of BIM-embedded visualization as visual support within the authoring software, and a smaller-scale architectural competition on my own.

The primary aim of this research is to showcase how these workflows can enhance design processes and outcomes while addressing future challenges. These enhancements aim to make BIM a more appealing design tool, improve project development, and provide accessible software. The target audience for these improvements includes design studios, architects, users, software developers, and students. The ultimate goal is to transform how we approach

architectural design by leveraging BIM's capabilities to optimize, streamline, and facilitate effective collaboration within the architectural design process.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/1s44jv5Lda4>

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